

COVINFORM

CORONAVIRUS VULNERABILITIES AND INFORMATION DYNAMICS RESEARCH AND MODELLING

D9.5 Videos

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Project

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Deliverable

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Executive Summary

Since the start of the COVID-19 pandemic, far-reaching consequences have been observed across the globe. Nevertheless, the effects of COVID-19 are far beyond physical health. Furthermore, the extent of the impact on individuals and communities varied depending on multiple factors.

The first animated COVINFORM video aims to highlight the project's intersectional approach toward the analysis of the COVID-19 pandemic and discusses the different forces influencing its impact.

The video targets our main communication audience – the general public. The video will act as a tool purposefully designed to attract the attention of the chosen audience and further raise awareness about the objectives of the COVINFORM project.

The video starts with an introduction to the start of the pandemic and further stresses its unequal impact on communities and marginalised groups. Consequently, the theory of intersectionality is introduced and explained. Conclusively, COVINFORM's approach to the research of the pandemic is explained, emphasising the project's research and other activities.

In addition to the first project video, COVINFORM has also published the recording of a joint webinar on “Vaccination refusal among healthcare workers”, co-organised with the NO-FEAR project, and two interviews, one on vaccinations in Israel and one on the Italian vaccine development. The latest bi-monthly report in March 2022 is also provided in video form.

All COVINFORM videos can be watched on our YouTube channel: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC2rwiA2bNVR52tRPVszdaXA>

This report describes the videos that have been made for the project so far and will be followed by a second iteration in April 2023.

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1 Introduction

In our Communication plan (D9.2), videos have been identified as a tool to raise awareness of the project and its topics, establish an online presence, and potentially reach a broad demographic. Additionally, the nature of the medium enables the COVINFORM project to communicate key messages in a simple form, encouraging the audience to meet the project and possibly engage with other communication materials.

D9.5 Videos is a demonstrator deliverable, which describes the videos that have been developed within the project so far. The second iteration of this deliverable (D9.9), due in M30 (30/4/2023), will describe the further progress of the project and video content production.

2 The videos

Videos are a way to present COVINFORM and its outcomes to all intended target audiences. They allow the communication of scientific outcomes and insights accessibly and understandably. Over the course of the project, we will create and publish three videos to communicate key insights and outcomes from the project in an accessible and interesting way. However, additional videos, such as recordings of webinars and interviews will also be produced. All our videos are and will be published on our YouTube channel, the project website, and promoted via the different channels, especially social media.

At the time of writing the first iteration of this deliverable, we have produced the first project video and published three recordings, which include a webinar and two interviews, as well as a bi-monthly report in video format, which looks back at two years of the pandemic through interviews with COVINFORM's practitioner partners.

2.1 First project video

The first step in developing the first project video was to define its concept. The video aims to accomplish two objectives. Firstly, to introduce the COVINFORM project and secondly to emphasise the unique intersectional approach that the project adopts.

The concept of the video focuses on highlighting the intersectional approach towards the analysis of the COVID-19 pandemic. Firstly, the COVID-19 pandemic is introduced, followed by a segment on how the pandemic affected vulnerable groups. The emphasis on the absence of marginalised communities in dialogues about policies will stress the need for an intersectional approach.

The second part of the video closely examines the origins of the intersectional approach and how we can benefit from it when applied as a form of analysis. Lastly, the video concludes with a proposed solution to the outlined issues. By outlining the unique research approach and research objectives of the COVINFORM project in the last section of the video, we further accentuate the project's activities.

2.2 Webinar recordings and interviews

To date, COVINFORM has published a recording of a joint webinar and two interviews.

The webinar was organised in collaboration with the NO-FEAR project and covers the important topic of "Vaccination refusal among healthcare workers".

The first interview includes perspectives on the vaccinations in Israel from Chaim Rafalowski, (Magen David Adom in Israel), and was conducted by Elena Ambrosetti and Marina Zannella (Sapienza University of Rome).

The second one is about the Italian vaccine development and Prof. Beatrice Vallone (Sapienza University of Rome) is interviewed by Donatella Strangio (Sapienza University of Rome).

2.3 Video availability

Our videos are available to view on the COVINFORM YouTube channel: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC2rwiA2bNVRs2tRPVszdaXA>.

The videos are further embedded on the COVINFORM website.

3 Conclusion

The first project video was produced as a joint effort of TRI and SYNNO. TRI initiated the process of video-making by putting together the concept and a script, which has been then used for the storyboard (see ANNEX). SYNNO provided their expertise for the video production to produce the animation.

The final product is an animated video highlighting the COVINFORM project and its intersectional approach to the analysis of the impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic.

ANNEX. Storyboard

Audio	Picture	Explanation
Since 2019, the world has been experiencing an unprecedented situation.		show globe
The Covid-19 pandemic has changed the course of our everyday lives across the globe.		globe turns into virus
We have faced a new challenge requiring a quick collaborative response in order to protect our lives.		zooming out; globe gets sprayed with disinfection spray
Two years into the pandemic, we can investigate different government approaches to regulations and restrictions relating to Covid-19 and their effectiveness.		show government building; around the building symbols of regulations
However, the impact of Covid-19 has been far greater than just on our health.		show diagram with people on it
We can safely say that the events deepened existing inequalities and vulnerabilities within society.		parts of the diagram get separated
The absence of inclusion of marginalised communities in the dialogue about policies exposes them to substantial health risks and the risk of being socially stigmatised.		part gets further separated and people on it are shown closer
The concept of intersectionality enables us to consider different axes of oppressions operating and developing unique ways in which people experience inequality.		marginalised people are shown

Audio	Picture	Explanation
<p>With origins in Black feminism, intersectionality considers how social factors, such as gender, race, sexuality, ethnicity, class or religion, merge to create modes of discrimination and privilege.</p>		<p>people are faded into sections</p>
<p>The intersectionality framework has been used to critically analyse the interconnections and interdependencies of social and political identities</p>		<p>zoom in on one circle</p>
<p>since it was first coined by Kimberle Crenshaw in 1982.</p>		<p>Kimberle Crenshaw is shown</p>
<p>The COVINFORM project applies an intersectional lens to understand the impact of COVID-19 response on vulnerable communities, taking into account the multitude of inequalities that determine the impact of the pandemic."</p>		<p>covinform intro is faded in</p>
<p>"Which brings us the question: how can we meaningfully appreciate the nuances of vulnerability when considering such far-reaching policies?"</p>		<p>lonely person sits on policy papers</p>
<p>How can we tailor our approaches to both understand and accommodate the voices of marginalised communities?</p>		<p>person with black shield is shown; black shield gets wiped and „help“ is shown</p>
<p>Within this context, COVINFORM examines how national governments, public health actors and communities have reacted to the pandemic.</p>		<p>show screens and info</p>
<p>The project also investigates communication strategies, practices to communicate risk, and how to utilise open data to paint a more holistic picture of vulnerability across selected European contexts</p>		<p>show icons</p>

Audio	Picture	Explanation
<p>COVINFORM consortium has already published several bi-monthly reports, country reports, webinars and a whitepaper discussing communication in the time of crisis.</p>		<p>show reports</p>
<p>Overall, the research of the COVINFORM project will help policymakers</p>		<p>data is changing to covinform logo</p>
<p>to design effective and inclusive responses, learn from best practices, and improve communication strategies in this and any other future crises</p>		<p>shield against covid</p>
<p>*Partner and contact as outro</p>		